

ON THE STUDY OF POLYHALIDES. PART V. THE STRUCTURE OF POLYHALIDES.

BY SUSIL KUMAR RAY AND DURGADAS MAJUMDAR.

In spite of investigations extending over a period of more than a century the constitution of the polyhalides is still a matter of much controversy. Attempts at elucidating the structure of these compounds have not as yet been very successful nor has any systematic investigation been made in this direction.

By studying the reactions of *para*-bromophenyltrimethylammonium trihalides, Reade (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 141; 1924, 125, 148; 1926, 2528) proposed the following structure for the trihalides :

where Q_m stands for the organic cation and X_1 , X_2 , X_3 for the halogen atoms which may be all different or two similar and one different.

From studies in absorption band spectra Lowry and Sass (*ibid.*, 1926, 622) have confirmed the observations of Crymble, Stewart and Wright (*Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1183) that KI_3 and CHI_3 have similar absorption band. No similarity is exhibited by any of the conventional formulæ for the polyhalides and iodoform, the most plausible structure for the former being that given by Reade. Further studies in the absorption spectra of the polyhalides by Goldstein and Lowry (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1092) have led these authors to confirm the structure given by Reade (*loc. cit.*).

Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 213; 1934, 11, 115) from observations of the variations in the equilibrium constant of reactions

(where R stands for H, Na, K, etc., and X stands for a halogen) suggested the structure of a trihalide to be

where X_1 stands for the halogen ion and X_2 for the halogen molecule. According to Ray (*loc. cit.*) the union between the halogen ion and the halo-

gen molecule is of an electrostatic nature. This structure, it will be observed, has some similarity to that suggested by Reade.

The first attempt to explain the structure from the standpoint of the electronic theory of valency was made by Gray and Dakers (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, 11, 81). They have measured the diamagnetic susceptibilities of the tetraalkylammonium polyhalides, prepared by Chattaway and Hoyle (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 654) and of the phenyltrimethylammonium polyhalides, prepared by Reade (*loc. cit.*). On the evidence of their observation, Gray and Dakers adopted the co-ordination theory of Werner and hence gave the structure,

for the trihalide, where M stands for a cation and X for any halogen excepting fluorine.

The possibility of the presence of single electron linkages in the polyhalide molecule was suggested by Cremer and Duncan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 181) but no experimental evidence was given by these authors. The provisional structure of Cremer and Duncan should be

where M stands for the cation and X for any halogen.

From the investigations on the structure of the polyhalides it will be observed that up till now only two structures have been given from the standpoint of the electronic theory of valency. The one suggested by Gray and Dakers (*loc. cit.*) assumes that the halogen atoms are linked together by electron-pair bonds or normal co-valency, while the other put forward by Cremer and Duncan (*loc. cit.*) assumes that the bonds are single electron bonds. The object of the present paper is to decide between the structures proposed by Gray and Dakers and by Cremer and Duncan and to attempt to derive a structure of the polyhalides based on the Quantum mechanical theory of homopolar valency of Heitler and London. Since the single electron linkage hypothesis was put forward by Sugden from parachor studies, the determination of the parachor of the polyhalides will be the best method for deciding whether such linkages are present or not, and in the present paper this method has been resorted to. As the polyhalides studied decompose on fusion, Sugden's original method for the determination of the parachor of solid substances is not applicable here and hence

the surface tension and density were determined in solution and the parachor calculated (Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 672, 843; 1935, 12, 248, 404).

The polyhalides of the alkali metals of lower atomic weight are known in solution in the form of equilibrium mixtures and they can not be isolated in the pure state, while the polyhalides of the alkali metals of higher atomic weights will not be soluble in organic solvents and in aqueous solution they would most likely dissociate into ions. Moreover, the atomic parachor of the alkali metals are not reliable. So in the present paper the polyhalides of the substituted ammonium radical have been investigated which have the advantages of being stable at the ordinary temperature and also soluble in non-dissociating organic solvents.

Since the parachor is affected widely by association or dissociation, it is necessary to ascertain that such disturbing effects are not occurring. This has been done by the determination of the molecular weights of the substances by the freezing point method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparations.

The compounds were prepared either according to the method of Reade or of Chattaway and Hoyle. Since the presence of slight impurities affect the surface tension widely, it is necessary that the substances should be in a high state of purity. The final compound as well as the intermediate compounds were repeatedly crystallised till a constant melting point was attained. One new compound was prepared in course of this investigation, its molecular formula was established by analysis and determination of molecular weight; its parachor was also determined. The following is the list of compounds prepared and studied.

(i) *Tetraethylammonium Tri-iodide* was crystallised from boiling alcohol till the constant melting point of 142° reached (Chattaway and Hoyle, m.p. 142°).

(ii) *Tetraethylammonium Iododibromide*, after three crystallisations from alcohol had a constant m.p. at 125° (Chattaway and Hoyle, m.p., 125° ; Gray and Dakers, m.p. 124°).

(iii) *p-Bromophenyltrimethylammonium Iododichloride*, after three crystallisations from glacial acetic acid, had a constant m.p. at 178° (Reade, m.p. 177°).

(iv) *p-Bromophenyltrimethylammonium Iodotetrachloride*, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, had m.p. 190° (Reade, m.p. $188-89^{\circ}$).

(v) *p*-Bromophenyltrimethylammonium Tribromide crystallised from glacial acetic acid below 80° , m.p., 175° (Reade, m.p. 175°).

(vi) Tetraethylammonium Iodobromotrichloride.—Pure iodine (6 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) in a small flask cooled to about 15° and into this was passed pure and dry chlorine gas. The passage of chlorine was continued till crystals of iodine trichloride separated. The current of chlorine was then stopped and the supernatant liquid decanted off. Tetraethylammonium bromide (9 g.), crystallised from water was suspended in acetic acid and was added to the precipitate of iodine trichloride. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath to 80° and acetic acid added little by little till all solid matter dissolved. The solution on cooling yielded yellow crystals of tetraethylammonium iodobromotrichloride which were thrice recrystallised from glacial acetic acid when it had the constant m.p. of 171° . The substance is insoluble in water but fairly soluble in alcohol, nitrobenzene and acetic acid. It decomposes in pyridine. [0.2144 g. gave 0.4206 g. of silver halides; $N(C_2H_5)_4 IBrCl_3$ requires 0.4136 g.] [Found: N, 2.98. $N(Et_4) IBrCl_3$ requires 3.15 per cent].

(vii) Tetramethylammonium Pentaiodide crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 130° (Chattaway and Hoyle, m.p. 130°).

Determination of Molecular Weight.

From the existing literature, it appears that the molecular weights of the polyhalides have not been determined. The usual method of establishing the formation of a definite compound in this line was by analysis of the compounds and seeing whether they fitted in the law of multiple proportions. This method leaves the question open that the substances might be eutectic mixtures. A determination of the molecular weights of these compounds will settle this point, as eutectic mixtures can not give results corresponding to normal molecular weight; the cryoscopic method for the determination of molecular weights has been adopted. The solubility of the polyhalides in the usual solvents is not very great and it was found that they were in general moderately soluble in nitrobenzene (*vide* Nernst, "Theoretical Chemistry," English Translation by L.W. Codd, p, 167). In the present investigation nitrobenzene, purified by repeated distillation, was employed as the solvent.

A Beckmann thermometer graduated to $1/100$ th of degree was used. The temperature of the bath was kept only one degree below the freezing point of the solution. By careful stirring the supercooling of the solution was never allowed to exceed 0.1° . The results are tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I.

Compound.	Wt. in 100 g. of nitrobenzene.	Depression of freezing point.	M.W. (obs.)	M.W. (calc.)	
NBt ₄ I ₃	0.9756	0.135	511		
	1.9780	0.275	508.6		
	2.5046	0.350	505.9		
			Mean	508.5	511
NBt ₄ IBr ₃	0.9854	0.170	409.9		
	1.9805	0.340	411.7		
	2.5046	0.425	416.7		
			Mean	412.7	417
C ₆ H ₄ Br.NMe ₃ ICl ₂	0.9232	0.160	408.0		
	1.8500	0.315	415.3		
	3.6021	0.625	407.4		
			Mean	410.2	413.0
C ₆ H ₄ Br.NMe ₃ ICl ₄	0.8954	0.135	468.9		
	1.7810	0.265	475.2		
	2.3259	0.340	483.7		
			Mean	475.9	484.0
C ₆ H ₄ Br.NMe ₃ Br ₃	0.5672	0.090	445.7		
	1.8070	0.285	448.3		
	2.2590	0.355	449.9		
			Mean	448.0	455.0
NBt ₄ IBrCl ₃	1.1210	0.180	440.2		
	3.5160	0.565	439.9		
	4.3981	0.705	441.1		
			Mean	440.4	443.5
NMe ₄ I ₅	1.252	0.175	505.8		
	2.593	0.400	458.2		
	3.125	0.595	368.5	709.0	

Thus, with the exception of NMe₄I₅, which apparently decomposes, the molecular weights of the other compounds obtained experimentally agree closely with that calculated from analytical data.

Determination of Parachor.

The parachor of the above mentioned compounds were determined in solution by the method of Ray (*loc. cit.*). The first, second and the last compound were found to be very soluble in pyridine and so parachor determination of these compounds have been carried out in pyridine. With the exception of the sixth compound, which decomposes in pyridine and has

therefore been investigated in nitrobenzene, the solubility of the other compounds was higher in nitrobenzene than in pyridine, and as such have been investigated in nitrobenzene. Pyridine used in this investigation was purified by distillation and then stored over pure caustic potash sticks in a stoppered bottle. Nitrobenzene was also similarly purified and then stored over pure fused calcium chloride. Dry and powdered substances whose parachor was to be determined were taken in 25 c.c. measuring flask (previously weighed empty and dry) and the total weight determined. The substance was dissolved in corresponding solvent and the weight of the solution determined. From these weighings the molar fraction of the solute was directly obtained.

The surface tension was determined by the maximum bubble pressure method. Altogether five to seven readings were taken on the manometer and the mean of all these readings was used in the calculation of the surface tension. The densities of the solutions were measured by means of a 10 c.c. stoppered pycnometer. The results are tabulated in Tables II-VIII. In these tables P_{pair} represents the value of the parachor calculated on the basis that the bonds between the halogen atoms are electron-pair bonds or normal co-valency, while P_{single} is the value calculated on the basis that the bonds are single electron linkages. In the following tables x is the mol. fraction of the solute, M_m , the mean molecular weight of the solution, P_m , the parachor of the solution, P_x , the parachor of the solute, d , the density and σ , the surface tension.

TABLE II.

Tetraethylammonium tri-iodide in pyridine.

x .	d .	σ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	P_{pair} .	P_{single} .
0.0	0.9696	34.69	79.00	197.7
0.008574	1.002	35.65	82.70	201.7	664.8
0.008696	1.003	35.81	82.74	201.8	666.8
0.01123	1.015	36.44	83.86	203.0	667.9
0.01265	1.015	35.79	84.46	203.5	656.1
0.01493	1.027	36.78	85.43	204.8	676.4
0.01763	1.033	35.45	86.61	206.0	669.4
0.01858	1.041	37.12	87.03	206.4	667.4
				Mean	666.9	664.3	641.1

TABLE III.

Tetraethylammonium iododibromide in pyridine.

α .	d .	σ .	M_m .	P_m	P_x .	P_{pair} .	P_{single} .
0°0	0·9696	34·69	79·00	197·7
0°01169	1·003	36·04	82·94	202·6	615·9
0°01255	1·007	36·31	83·23	202·9	613·7
0°01963	1·023	36·49	85·63	205·8	611·3
0°02371	1·030	36·45	87·00	207·5	611·6
0°02489	1·034	36·85	87·40	208·3	622·6
0°03230	1·050	36·93	89·90	211·1	613·1
				Mean	614·8	618·3	595·1

TABLE IV.

p-Bromophenyltrimethylammonium iododichloride in PhNO₂.

α .	d .	σ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	P_{pair} .	P_{single} .
0°0	1·198	44·30	123·0	264·9
0°004573	1·207	44·70	124·4	266·5	612·4
0°004594	1·206	44·54	124·4	266·5	609·5
0°006451	1·208	44·50	124·9	267·1	620·0
0°007158	1·208	44·40	125·1	267·4	628·7
0°008682	1·214	45·16	125·5	268·0	622·0
0°009464	1·214	44·82	125·7	268·2	622·0
0°009574	1·211	44·42	125·8	268·2	616·3
				Mean	618·7	619·7	596·5

TABLE V.

p-Bromophenyltrimethylammonium iodotetrachloride in PhNO₂.

α .	d .	σ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	P_{pair} .	$P_{sing \tau}$.
0.0	1.198	44.30	123.0	264.9
0.002952	1.206	44.79	124.1	266.2	711.2
0.003639	1.207	44.75	124.4	266.6	714.5
0.006551	1.211	44.80	125.4	267.9	732.6
0.006736	1.214	45.20	125.5	268.1	742.3
0.008175	1.214	44.87	126.0	268.6	721.8
				Mean	724.4	728.3	693.5

TABLE VI.

Tetraethylammonium iodobromotrichloride in PhNO₂.

α .	d .	σ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	P_{pair} .	P_{single} .
0.0	1.198	44.30	123.0	264.9
0.009665	1.203	43.48	126.1	269.2	713.9
0.01206	1.208	44.00	126.8	270.4	721.4
0.01592	1.213	43.89	128.2	272.0	709.8
0.01786	1.215	44.01	128.7	272.9	716.6
0.01984	1.218	44.01	129.4	273.7	710.8
				Mean	714.5	713.2	678.4

TABLE VII.

p-Bromophenyltrimethylammonium tribromide in PhNO₂.

α .	d .	σ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	P_{pair} .	P_{single} .
0.0	1.198	44.30	123.0	264.9	—		
0.004054	1.199	43.53	124.3	266.3	616.6		
0.004862	1.201	43.65	124.6	266.7	637.7		
0.005064	1.201	43.73	124.7	266.8	631.9		
0.006068	1.204	43.61	125.1	267.0	625.2		
				Mean	628.1	624.1	600.9

TABLE VIII.

Tetraethylammonium pentaiodide in pyridine.

α .	d .	σ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	P_{pair} .	P_{single} .
0'0	0'9696	34'69	79'00	197'7	—		
0'004619	1'001	36'23	81'90	200'8	866'2		
0'006060	1'010	32'96	82'82	196'4	—		
0'007109	1'021	38'23	83'47	203'3	984'7		
0'008390	1'022	31'76	84'29	195'8	—		
0'01361	1'042	38'15	87'58	208'8	1014'0		
				Mean	—	691'9	645'5

DISCUSSION.

From the preceding tables it will be seen that the parachor values of the compounds obtained experimentally agree very closely to the value calculated on the assumption that the bonds between the halogens are electron-pair bonds. In the case of tetraethylammonium pentaiodide the data obtained (Table VIII) will show that the values are far from being constant. The determination of the molecular weight showed that the substance decomposes in solution and the erratic nature of the parachor values is apparently due to this decomposition. The investigation of the magnetic susceptibilities of this compound by Gray and Dakers (*loc. cit.*) did not tally with their theory. It may also be mentioned here that according to Ephraim ("Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry", English Ed., 1934, p. 217) polyiodides higher than tri-iodides do not exist. The alleged higher iodides are solid solutions of iodine in tri-iodide and probably eutectic mixtures.

While the parachor values show that the bonds between the halogens are electron-pair bonds, corresponding structures can not be given from the classical electronic theory of valency of Lewis and Kossel. An attempt will be made to derive a structure of the polyhalides based on the quantum mechanical theory of Heitler and London. London (*Z. Physik*, 1928, 46, 455) in extending this theory put forward that the variable valency of elements can be explained by supposing that the electron configuration of the atom varies from compound to compound so that the number of

electrons with unpaired spins varies; the limitation to such variation being given by the exclusion rule of Pauli. The halogen atoms have the structure $n s^2 p^5$, of the valency shell, where n stands for 2, 3, 4 or 5 in the cases of fluorine, chlorine, bromine or iodine. Corresponding to these structures there can be only one electron with unpaired spin in the atom and as such the halogens are monovalent in most of the compounds. Except fluoride all other halogens exhibit polyvalency. To explain this London assumes that the following electron configurations are possible without violating Pauli's rule, *viz.*,

where n stands for 3, 4 or 5 corresponding to chlorine, bromine or iodine. In the case of fluorine no other structure is possible without violating Pauli's rule and hence fluorine is consistently monovalent. Corresponding to the first, second or third of the structures suggested by London, the halogens can be tri-, penta- or heptavalent.

As has been already pointed out that Werner and Reade also put forward the suggestion that one halogen atom in the tri-halide acts as the kernel atom round which the other halogen atoms and the positive radical are co-ordinated. On London's theory of valency of the halogens to this central kernel atom can be ascribed the valencies 3, 5 or 7 in the tri-, penta-, or hepta-halides. The structures of the polyhalides are therefore

where R stands for the univalent positive radical and X , for either chlorine, bromine or iodine. The double arrows stand for electron-pair bonds and the opposite directions represent opposite spin.

The above mentioned electron configurations of the kernel halogen atom shows that incomplete electron sub-shells are being formed due to polyhalide formation. As is well known, the paramagnetic properties of the rare earths and the transition series elements are due to the presence of

incomplete electron sub-shells so the kernel atom in the polyhalides should be expected to show paramagnetism due to the change in the electron configuration on polyhalide formation. This has been experimentally verified by the work of Gray and Dakers (*loc. cit.*). They found that the diamagnetic susceptibilities of the polyhalides calculated from the values of the atomic diamagnetic susceptibilities and the additivity rule, are always in excess of the values obtained experimentally. This is evidently due to the development of feeble paramagnetism. Thus the magnetic susceptibilities of the polyhalides furnish strong evidence for the structure suggested in this paper.

In the case of the polyhalides of the alkali metals of lower atomic weight and metals of alkaline earths, Ray (*loc. cit.*) suggested a structure based on the theory of electrostatic attraction. The properties of the polyhalides of the alkali metals and substituted ammonium radicals are different in more than one respect; the former are soluble in water but sparingly soluble in non-dissociating organic solvents and they are more or less unstable, while the latter are insoluble in water but soluble in non-polar organic solvents and are fairly stable. From this it appears that there is some probability of a structural difference between these two series of compounds and that polyhalides of the alkali metals and metals of alkaline earths contain polar linkages and with the increase in the volume of the cation, the polar property gradually diminishes until in the case of the substituted ammonium polyhalides the linkage becomes a co-valent one.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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